

The Effect of Job Motivation, Work Environment and Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Job Satisfaction and Public Service Quality in Magetan, East Java, Indonesia

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Abstract—Magetan area is going to be the object of this research which is located in East Java, Indonesia. The data were obtained from 270 civil servants working at the Magetan District government. The data were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling with Partial Least Square program. The research showed the following findings: (1) job motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB); (2) work environment has positive and significant effect on OCB; (3) leadership variable has positive and significant effect on OCB; (4) job motivation variable has no significant effect on job satisfaction; (5) work environment variable has no significant effect on job satisfaction; (6) leadership variable has no significant effect on job satisfaction; (7) OCB is positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction; (8) job satisfaction variable is positively and significantly correlated with quality of public service at the Magetan District government.

Keywords—Job Satisfaction, Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Quality of Public Service

I. INTRODUCTION

MAGETAN District as one of the districts in East Java province of course with all the capabilities has attempted to provide the best services to community. But within the last two years since the Year of Public Service Improvement which was launched in 2004, the Magetan district has been proved less successful in terms of public service when compared with other District/Municipal Governments in East Java. Of the 38 Districts in East Java based on the results of research conducted by The Jawa Pos Institute of Autonomi about public services in 38 districts and municipalities in East Java, which is measured using three parameters: health service, educational service, and

administrative service in 2008 and 2009, the Magetan district ranked 24th and 31st for health service category, ranked 17th and 14th for the educational service category, and ranked 8th and 10th for the administrative service category.

Job satisfaction can be accomplished by providing motivation to employees. Motivation is the desire within a person that encourages him/her to perform an action, where one often takes an action to achieve a particular goal [8]. The results of research by [12] show that motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction and work practices in the field, while the results of research by [1] suggest that job motivation has positive and non significant effect on employee satisfaction.

Job satisfaction can also be created through a good work environment. Theoretically, [6] states that employee wants a good workplace because this conducive workplace will lead to physical enjoyment or pleasure. The results of study by [16] show that the work environment will determine employee satisfaction in which the good work environment will increase employee satisfaction.

Job satisfaction of employee can also be created through a proper application of leadership concepts. [9] states that the concept of proper leadership can create employee satisfaction so as to create conducive atmosphere for employees in improving quality of service to customers or the public. The results of studies by [20] and [16] indicate that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee satisfaction.

Work behavior or known as OCB in the organization that is committed to improving service quality is also very important to be developed or nurtured. Furthermore, [14] states that employees who feel satisfied are more likely to speak positively about the organization, help others, and far exceeds normal expectations in their work. The results of studies by [16], [21], [20], [18] and [7] all suggest that job satisfaction is positively and significantly associated with OCB.

This study tries to analyze and examine empirically the influence of job motivation, work environment, and the leadership on OCB and job satisfaction, and the effect of job

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satisfaction on the quality of public services in Magetan district. This research topic is chosen with consideration that the results of the empirical study conducted by the author showing a disparity in research results (*research gap*) between the researches of [12] and [1]. The findings of [12] show that job motivation is positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction, while the results of the study by [1] show that job motivation has positive and non-significant effect on job satisfaction. By ignoring the place, time and object of research that allow these disparities to occur, this study will review the relationship between job motivation and job satisfaction, especially among civil servants in Magetan district.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS

A. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework of this research show in fig 1,

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

Where,

- JM : Job Motivation
- WE : Work Environment
- LS : Leadership
- OCB : Organizational Citizenship Behaviour
- JS : Job Satisfaction
- PSQ : Public Service Quality

B. Hypotheses

Based on Conceptual Framework, hypotheses of this research are:

The first hypothesis states that the job motivation is significantly associated with OCB in Magetan District Government.

The second hypothesis states that the work environment significantly influences the OCB among civil servants in Magetan District Government.

The third hypothesis says that leadership is significantly associated with OCB in Magetan District Government.

The fourth hypothesis says that job motivation has a significant impact on job satisfaction in Magetan District Government

The fifth hypothesis says that work environment or workplace has a significant effect on job satisfaction at Magetan District Government.

The sixth hypothesis says that the leadership is significantly associated with job satisfaction at Magetan District Government.

Seventh hypothesis says that OCB is significantly related to the job satisfaction at Magetan District Government.

Eighth hypothesis states that job satisfaction significantly influences the quality of public services in Magetan District Government.

III. METHOD AND DATA

The population in this study includes all Civil Servants working in institutions of Magetan district, consisting of six offices, six departments, three agencies, one regional hospital, and 16 sub-districts with the rank levels from Grade II to Grade IV, involving as many as 5402 people.

Sampling technique used was the *proportional stratified random sampling* that takes samples from each agency randomly and proportionally at 5%. The proportional sampling technique (*proportional sampling*) was conducted to refine the use of sampling technique in which the number of subjects in each agency is not the same. Therefore, to obtain a representative sample, the sampling at each institution was determined equal or proportional to the number of subjects at each institution [2]. Based on the [17], the samples to be taken in this research were 270 respondents (5402 x 5%).

A research variable is an attribute or the nature or value of people, object, or activity that has a certain variation defined to be studied and drawn its conclusion by the researcher [17]. Classification of variables in this study is shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 CLASSIFICATION OF THE RESEARCH VARIABLES

Hy	CLASSIFICATION OF THE RESEARCH VARIABLES	
p	Exogenous Variables	Endogenous Variables
H1	Job motivation (X ₁)	OCB (Y ₁)
H2	Work environment (X ₂)	OCB (Y ₁)
H3	Leadership (X ₃)	OCB (Y ₁)
H4	Job motivation (X ₁)	Job satisfaction (Y ₂)
H5	Work environment (X ₂)	Job satisfaction (Y ₂)
H6	Leadership (X ₃)	Job satisfaction (Y ₂)
H7	OCB (Y ₁)	Job satisfaction (Y ₂)
H8	Job satisfaction (Y ₂)	Public service quality (Y ₃)

Classification of latent variables and measured variables in this research is showed in Table II.

TABLE II
 CLASSIFICATION OF LATENT AND MEASURED VARIABLES

Latent variables	Measured variables
1. Job motivation (X ₁)	1.1 Expectation (X _{1,1}) 1.2 Instrumentality (X _{1,2}) 1.3 Valence (X _{1,3})
2. Work environment (X ₂)	2.1 Work Facility (X _{2,1}) 2.2 Work Infrastructure (X _{2,2}) 2.3 Coworkers (X _{2,3})
3. Leadership (X ₃)	3.1 Charisma (X _{3,1}) 3.2 Inspiration (X _{3,2}) 3.3 Intellectual Stimulus (X _{3,3}) 3.4 Individualized attention (X _{3,4})
4. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y ₁)	4.1 Altruism (Y _{1,1}) 4.2 Conscientiousness (Y _{1,2}) 4.3 Positive attitude (Y _{1,3}) 4.4 Courtesy (Y _{1,4}) 4.5 Civic virtue (Y _{1,5})
5. Job satisfaction (Y ₂)	5.1 The job itself (Y _{2,1}) 5.2 Job promotion (Y _{2,2}) 5.3 Coworkers (Y _{2,3}) 5.4 Work condition (Y _{2,4})
6. Public service quality (Y ₃)	6.1 Tangibles (Y _{3,1}) 6.2 Reliability (Y _{3,2}) 6.3 Responsiveness (Y _{3,3}) 6.4 Assurance (Y _{3,4}) 6.5 Empathy (Y _{3,5})

Questionnaires were used as tool to collect data from respondents. Each variable was measured by scoring according to Likert scale. It is a method of measuring the respondents' stance by stating approval or disapproval toward variables measured, which is described in the existing statements in the questionnaire. Likert scale employed in this study uses five valuation points where point 1 shows the lowest value and point 5 indicates the highest value.

This research was conducted in Magetan district in East Java province, involving 6 offices, 6 departments, 3 Agencies, 1 hospital and 16 sub-districts in Magetan district government in East Java province. Activities in this study were carried out starting from April 2009 and were expected to be completed on February 2010.

The sampling and data collection were carried out through questionnaire design and distribution of questionnaires to respondents. The data used were primary and secondary.

Primary data were data from respondents collected directly by researcher in the field, obtained from the questionnaires distributed to civil servants in Magetan district of East Java who were selected as respondents here. Secondary data were provided by the relevant agencies related to the research object. The secondary data derived from other relevant sources including Central Bureau of Statistics, the Office of Archives and Library, and others.

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) can answer the question of causality in structural and dimensional model. The researcher may be confronted with the research question of identifying the dimensions of a concept/construct, while at the same time he/she wants to measure the effect or degree of relationship among the factors whose dimensions have been identified [3].

In this study, SEM analysis was used with the *Partial Least Square* (PLS) method. Data don't necessarily have a normal multivariate distribution and sample size must not be necessarily large [5]. While PLS can also be used to confirm the theory, it can also be used to describe/predict whether or not there is correlation between the latent variables whose theoretical support is still tentative, or each latent variable is newly measured, so it places more emphasis on data rather than theory. Thus the advantage of this PLS method is that it can be used for developing a theory for predictive purpose [5].

Validity test is defined as a measure that shows the degree of validity of instrument. Valid instrument has high validity. Conversely, the less valid instrument possesses low validity. An instrument is considered valid when it can measure what is desired. An instrument is regarded valid when it can reveal the data of the variable appropriately investigated. High or low validity indicates the extent to which the collected data do not deviate from the validity in question [2].

In this study, validity testing was conducted to determine whether or not an indicator/item is valid in which this can be seen from the results of *t* test, namely when the *t*-statistic value is greater than 1.96 (*t*-statistic > 1.96) suggesting that the indicator/item is valid.

Reliability test (*construct reliability*) was used to determine whether an instrument is reliable to be used as a means of collecting data because the instrument is good enough. Reliability shows a degree of reliability. Reliable means trustworthy or dependable. A phrase stating that the instrument must be reliable in fact implies that the instrument is well sufficient to disclose reliable data [2]. In this study, reliability testing was performed to determine whether or not an indicator/item is reliable in which a reliability of indicator/item can be seen from the *composite reliability*, i.e., if the *composite reliability* value is greater than 0.5 (composite reliability > 0.5) it means that such an indicator or item is reliable. Validity test (*construct validity*) and reliability test (*construct reliability*) were done with the aid of PLS program. Descriptions of Respondents for this research are:

A. Age

Respondents selected as samples in this research are civil servants in Magetan district in East Java province involving 270 people. The frequency distribution of respondents by age is shown in Table III.

TABLE III
 FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY AGE

Age (year)	interval	Frequency	Percentage (%)
23 – 28		54	20.0
29 – 34		72	26.7
35 – 40		55	20.3
41 – 46		76	28.2
> 46		13	4.8
Total		270	100

This suggests that majority of the respondents (67%) belong to the age group of 23-40 year, meaning that civil

servants of Magetan district in East Java province are in the productive age to work for a living for himself or his family.

B. Sex

Respondents making up of the sample total 270 respondents in which a detailed frequency distribution of respondents based on gender is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV
 FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY SEX

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 = Men	188	69.6
2 = Women	82	30.4
Total	270	100

Table IV shows that civil servants at Magetan district government are dominated by men than women, meaning that number of men who work is larger than their counterparts.

C. Education

Based on educational level of respondents, this research shows that most respondents have three-year education (bachelor) degree, as shown in Table V.

TABLE V
 FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY EDUCATION

Education	Frequency	(%)
1 = Junior high school	0	0
2 = Senior high school	64	23.7
3 = College/3-year education	103	38.1
4 = Undergraduate	87	32.2
5 = Postgraduate	16	5.9
Total	270	100

IV. RESULT

Evaluation Results of SEM Assumptions

A. Construct validity test

TABLE VI
 VALIDITY OF JOB MOTIVATION (X₁) CONSTRUCT

Latent Variable	Indicators	t-statistic	Conclusion (t-statistic > 1.96)
Job Motivation	X _{1,1}	12.564	Valid
	X _{1,2}	3.874	Valid
	X _{1,3}	5.424	Valid

Table VI shows that the t-statistic value of each indicator is greater than 1.96 (i.e. t-table value at significance level of 0.05). This value is considered valid. From these calculation we can conclude that all indicators of the job motivation (X₁) variable are valid (construct validity is fulfilled). This shows that the three indicators (observed variables) can be used as the dimension of job motivation variable.

TABLE VII
 VALIDITY OF WORK ENVIRONMENT (X₂) CONSTRUCT

Latent Variable	Indicators	t-statistic	Conclusion (t-statistic > 1,96)
Work environment	X _{2,1}	7.045	Valid
	X _{2,2}	11.302	Valid
	X _{2,3}	19.262	Valid

Table VII shows that the t-statistic value of each indicator is greater than 1.96. From this calculation we can conclude that all indicators of work environment (X₂) variable are valid (construct validity is fulfilled). This indicates that the three indicators (observed variables) can be used as dimension of the working environment variable.

TABLE VIII
 VALIDITY OF LEADERSHIP (X₃) CONSTRUCT

Latent Variable	Indicators	t-statistic	Conclusion (t-statistic > 1,96)
Leadership	X _{3,1}	3,591	Valid
	X _{3,2}	7,264	Valid
	X _{3,3}	2,868	Valid
	X _{3,4}	9,495	Valid

Table VIII shows that the t-statistic value of each indicator is greater than 1.96. This value is considered valid. From this calculation we can conclude that the entire indicators of the leadership (X₃) variable are valid (construct validity is fulfilled). This shows that the four indicators (observed variables) can be used as dimension of the leadership variable.

TABLE IX
 VALIDITY OF ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR (Y₁) CONSTRUCT

Latent Variable	Indicators	t-statistic	Conclusion (t > 1,96)
OrganizationalCitizenship Behavior	Y _{1,1}	12,988	Valid
	Y _{1,2}	7,342	Valid
	Y _{1,3}	8,623	Valid
	Y _{1,4}	15,501	Valid
	Y _{1,5}	13,564	Valid

Table IX shows that the t-statistic value of each indicator is greater than 1.96. This value is considered valid. From this calculation we can conclude that the entire indicators of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y₁) variable are valid. This shows that the five indicators (observed variables) can be used as dimension of the OCB variable.

TABLE X
 VALIDITY OF JOB SATISFACTION (Y₂) VARIABLE

Latent Variable	Indicators	t-statistic	Conclusion (t > 1,96)
Job satisfaction	Y _{2,1}	5,983	Valid
	Y _{2,2}	17,209	Valid
	Y _{2,3}	8,888	Valid
	Y _{2,4}	14,692	Valid

Table X shows that the t-statistic value of each indicator is greater than 1.96 (i.e., t-table value at 0.05 significance level). This value is considered valid. From this calculation we can

conclude that the entire indicators of the Job Satisfaction (Y_2) variable are valid (construct validity is fulfilled). This shows that the four indicators (observed variables) can be used as dimension of the job satisfaction variable.

TABLE XI
VALIDITY OF PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY (Y_3) CONSTRUCT

Latent Variable	Indicators	t-statistic	Conclusion (t-statistic > 1,96)
Public service quality	$Y_{3,1}$	7,190	Valid
	$Y_{3,2}$	3,552	Valid
	$Y_{3,3}$	3,264	Valid
	$Y_{3,4}$	7,500	Valid
	$Y_{3,5}$	8,662	Valid

Source: Processing results

Table XI shows that the t-statistic value of each indicator is greater than 1.96 (i.e., t-table value at 0.05 significance level). This value is considered valid. From this calculation we can conclude that the entire indicators of the public service quality (Y_3) variable are valid (construct validity is fulfilled). This shows that the five indicators (observed variables) can be used as dimension of the public service quality variable.

B. Construct Reliability Test

Results of construct reliability test are showed concisely in Table XII.

TABLE XII
RECAPITULATION OF RELIABILITY TESTING RESULTS

Latent Variables	Composite Reliability	Conclusion
1. Job motivation (X_1)	0,770	Reliable
2. Work environment (X_2)	0,866	Reliable
3. Leadership (X_3)	0,746	Reliable
4. OCB (Y_1)	0,899	Reliable
5. Job satisfaction (Y_2)	0,859	Reliable
6. Public service quality (Y_3)	0,820	Reliable

The result of calculation in Table XII shows the *composite reliability* values for each latent variable of job motivation, working environment, leadership, OCB, job satisfaction, and quality of public service which are greater than 0.5 (*composite reliability* > 0.5). From this calculation we can conclude that all of the research instruments are reliable, and can be used for further analysis.

V. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of the effect between Latent Variables

Once the research model is already accepted, then we perform a test to see if there is influence between the latent variables that have been hypothesized previously. The testing results of the influence between latent variables are shown in Fig 2 and Table XIII.

TABLE XIII
RESULTS OF SEM WITH PLS

Variables	Regression Weight	t-statistic	Conclusion (t-statistic > 1,96)
$JM(X_1) \rightarrow OCB(Y_1)$	0.284	2.541	Significant
$WE(X_2) \rightarrow OCB(Y_1)$	0.359	2.417	Significant
$LS(X_3) \rightarrow OCB(Y_1)$	0.322	2.244	Significant
$JM(X_1) \rightarrow JS(Y_2)$	0.093	0.791	Non Significant
$WE(X_2) \rightarrow JS(Y_2)$	0.172	1.015	Non Significant
$LS(X_3) \rightarrow JS(Y_2)$	0.144	1.058	Non Significant
$OCB(Y_1) \rightarrow JS(Y_2)$	0.528	3.310	Significant
$JS(Y_1) \rightarrow PSQ(Y_3)$	0.787	16.534	Significant

Fig. 2 Modeling Results of SEM with PLS

Hypothesis testing was done by comparing the *t-statistic* value of each latent variable with a t-table (1.96), the value is considered significant if the t-statistic value of latent variable is greater than 1.96. Fig 2 and Table XIII shows:

1. Job motivation (X_1) is positively and significantly associated with *organizational citizenship behavior* (Y_1), with a t-statistic value = 2.541 > 1.96 and has a regression coefficient value of 0.284.
2. Work environment (X_2) has positive and significant effect on *organizational citizenship behavior* (Y_1), with a t-statistic value = 2.417 > 1.96 and has a regression coefficient value of 0.359.
3. Leadership (X_3) has positive and significant effect on *organizational citizenship behavior* (Y_1), with a t-statistic value = 2.244 > 1.96 and has a regression coefficient value of 0.322.
4. Job motivation (X_1) does not significantly influence job satisfaction (Y_2) with a t-statistic value = 0.791 < 1.96.
5. Work environment (X_2) does not significantly influence job satisfaction (Y_2), with a t-statistic value = 1.015 < 1.96.
6. Leadership (X_3) does not significantly influence job satisfaction (Y_2) with a t-statistic value = 1.058 < 1.96.

7. Organizational citizenship behavior (Y1) is positively and significantly related to job satisfaction of (Y2) with a t-statistic value = 3.310 > 1.96 and has regression coefficient value of 0.528.

8. Job satisfaction (Y2) produces positive and significant effect on the quality of public services (Y3) with a t-statistic value = 16.534 > 1.96 and has a regression coefficient value of 0.787.

Contribution Analysis of Latent Variables Influence Table XIV shows:

1. About 66.4% variation in *organizational citizenship behavior* (Y1) in Magetan district Government of East Java province can be explained by the job motivation (X1), work environment (X2), and leadership (X3) variables.
2. About 69.5% variation in job satisfaction (Y2) in Magetan district can be explained by the job motivation (X1), workplace (X2), leadership (X3), and the Organizational citizenship behavior (Y1) variables.
3. About 61.9% variation in public service quality (Y3) in Magetan district can be explained by the job satisfaction (Y2).

TABLE XIV
COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION (R²)

Latent Variables	R ²	REMARK
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y ₁)	0.664	Job motivation (X1), workplace (X2), and leadership (X3) contributed 66.4% of variance to OCB (Y1), meaning that 66.4% of variance in Y1 can be explained by X1, X2, and X3.
Job Satisfaction (Y ₂)	0.695	Job motivation (X1), workplace (X2), leadership (X3), and OCB (Y1) contributed 69.5% of variance to job satisfaction (Y2), meaning that 69.5% of variance in Y2 can be explained by X1, X2, X3, and Y1.
Public Service Quality (Y ₃)	0.619	Job satisfaction (Y2) contributed 61.9% of variance to public service quality (Y3), meaning that 61.9% of variance in Y3 can be explained by the Y2.

B. Analysis of Direct Effect, Indirect and Total Effect

Strength of an effect between constructs, whether direct, indirect, or total effect, can be analyzed through a regression coefficient of all lines with one-end arrows. Analysis of the indirect effect (*standardized indirect effect*) of latent variable is intended to know the function or role of intervening variable, whether it can mediate the relationship (influence) between latent variables.

Intervening variable represents *mediating* variable whose function is to mediate the relationship between latent variables [4]. The analysis of direct and indirect effects is undertaken to know the function or role of intervening variable whether or not it takes role in mediating the relationship between the latent variables in this study. It's shown in table XV.

TABLE XV

Latent Variables	ANALYSIS OF DIRECT, INDIRECT AND TOTAL EFFECTS		
	Effect between Latent Variables		
	Direct	Indirect	Total
JM(X ₁)→OCB(Y ₁)	0.284(S)	-	0.284
WE(X ₂)→OCB(Y ₁)	0.359(S)	-	0.359
LS(X ₃)→OCB(Y ₁)	0.322(S)	-	0.322
JM(X ₁)→JS(Y ₂)	0.093(TS)	0.150(S)	0.243
WE(X ₂)→JS(Y ₂)	0.172(TS)	0.190(S)	0.362
LS(X ₃)→JS(Y ₂)	0.144(TS)	0.170(S)	0.314
OCB(Y ₁)→JS(Y ₂)	0.528(S)	-	0.528
JS(Y ₁)→PSQ(Y ₃)	0.787(S)	-	0.787

Analysis of direct, indirect and total effects can be explained as follows:

1. Job motivation (X1) is directly and positively correlated with OCB (Y1) at 0.284.
2. Work environment or workplace (X2) possesses direct and positive effects on OCB (Y1) at 0.359.
3. Leadership (X3) is directly and positively associated with OCB (Y1) of 0.322.
4. Job motivation (X1) has direct and positive effects on job satisfaction (Y2) at 0.093 but the effect is not significant.
5. Work environment (X2) has direct and positive effect on job satisfaction (Y2) at 0.172, but the effect is not significant.
6. Leadership (X3) has direct and positive effects on job satisfaction (Y2) at 0.144 but the effect is not significant.
7. OCB (Y1) has direct and positive influence on job satisfaction (Y2) at 0.528.
8. Job motivation (X1) has indirect, positive and significant effects on job satisfaction (Y2) through OCB (Y1) at 0.284 x 0.528 = 0.150, this effect is shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3 Relationship between job motivation (X₁), OCB (Y₁) and job satisfaction (Y₂)

Fig 3 shows the indirect effect of job motivation on job satisfaction, with indirect and positive effect at 0.150, and this effect is significant. Additionally, the job motivation possesses the direct effect on job satisfaction at .093 but the effect is not significant.

The results of this study indicate that *OCB* as an intervening variable takes a role in mediating the effect of job motivation (X1) on job satisfaction (Y2) in Magetan District, because:

- a. Making the effect of job motivation (X1) on job satisfaction (Y2) which is initially not significant to be significant.
- b. Making the effect of job motivation (X1) on job satisfaction (Y2) to be greater, namely from 0.093 to 0.150.

Indirectly the workplace/work environment (X2) is positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction

(Y₂) through OCB (Y₁), amounting to $0.359 \times 0.528 = 0.190$. This influence is shown in Fig 4.

Fig. 4 Relationship between work environment (X₂), OCB (Y₁) and job satisfaction (Y₂)

Fig 4 shows an indirect effect of the work environment on job satisfaction, with indirect effect of .190. The direct effect of work environment on job satisfaction is at 0.172, but the effect is not significant. Results of current research showed that OCB as intervening variable played a role of mediating the effect of work environment (X₂) on job satisfaction (Y₂) in Magetan district government, because:

- Making the effect of work environment (X₂) on job satisfaction (Y₂) which is initially not significant to be significant.
- Making the effect of work environment (X₂) on job satisfaction (Y₂) to be greater, namely from 0.172 to 0.190.

Indirectly, the leadership (X₃) is positively and significantly correlated with job satisfaction (Y₂) through OCB (Y₁) of $0.322 \times 0.528 = 0.170$, this effect is shown in Fig 5.

Fig. 5 Relationship between leadership (X₃), OCB (Y₁) and job satisfaction (Y₂)

Fig. 5 shows the indirect effect of the leadership on job satisfaction, with the indirect effect of .170; while the direct effect of leadership on job satisfaction is at .144 but the effect is not significant.

The results of this study indicate that OCB as intervening variable mediates the influence of the leadership (X₃) on job satisfaction (Y₂) in Magetan district because:

- Making the influence of leadership (X₃) on job satisfaction (Y₂) which is initially not significant to be significant.
- Making the influence of leadership (X₃) on job satisfaction (Y₂) to be greater, namely from 0.144 to 0.170.

VI. THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

There are several essential findings in this study described as follows:

1. Employee motivation has no significant direct effect on job satisfaction in Magetan district government. This likely is because most of the employees (96.8%) felt less satisfied with the job itself because the work is relatively easy to do and not varied (boring), less pleasant, and less relevant to their expertise/experiences and expectation. Such work condition doesn't motivate the employees in their work so that it doesn't produce significant impact on job satisfaction.

2. Work environment has no significant direct effect on job satisfaction among civil servants in Magetan district government. This likely is because most of the employees (65%) felt that the work environment is less supportive or less conducive, especially in terms of access from home to the workplace that they consider far enough. This less supportive work environment is less satisfactory to most of the employees thereby the work environment is not significantly related to the job satisfaction.

3. Leadership has no significant direct effect on job satisfaction among civil servants in Magetan district government. This is possibly due to most of the employees (92.9%) felt that the leader is less capable in terms of communicating the vision and mission and ways to accomplish them, less capable to instill a sense of pride to employees, and less capable to gain the respect and trust of their employees. Such leadership condition is certainly unsatisfactory to employees so that leadership is not significantly correlated with job satisfaction.

4. Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as an intervening variable takes a role in mediating the influence of job motivation, work environment, and leadership on job satisfaction among civil servants or employees in Magetan district government. Based on the results of the researcher's direct interview with a number of respondents, it is known that most employees in Magetan district consider organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as having high social and spiritual values.

From the interviews it can be concluded that the majority of employees in Magetan District government truly recognize that job satisfaction will not be obtained from motivation factor (in this case, salary), work environment and leadership. In carrying out their tasks, they help fellow employees in completing job duties, behave well and not harm others. This becomes a satisfaction for most employees. This possibly could explain why organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in this study may mediate the relationship between job motivation, work environment, leadership and job satisfaction.

VII. IMPLICATIONS OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

A. Theoretical Implications

As mentioned in previous sections this study was designed to test and analyze the causal relationships between job motivation, work environment, leadership, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), job satisfaction and quality of public services in Magetan district government.

Job motivation, work environment, and leadership have non-significant effect on job satisfaction. These research findings are inconsistent with the opinion of [19] who said that the motivation, workplace, and leadership can boost employee loyalty and job satisfaction. This indicates that now job satisfaction of the Civil Servants is not significantly related to their job motivation, work environment, and leadership, so that research findings are interesting to be investigated further, whether there is difference in the behavior of individuals in public organizations and other business organizations.

Job motivation, work environment, and leadership are significantly associated with OCB. The finding of this study is consistent with the opinion of [11] stating that job motivation is significantly correlated with OCB (creative work behavior), and opinion of [6] that a good working environment affects the effective and efficient behavior of employees or OCB.

Additionally, the finding of this study corroborates the results of research conducted [13] showing that transformational leadership is positively and significantly associated with organizational citizenship behavior through the mediating variable of trust and *procedural justice*.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has a significant impact on job satisfaction. The results of [15] suggest that job satisfaction is positively and significantly associated with organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), which is reflected in *altruism*. [20] shows that there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior (COB). This indicates that there is a reciprocal relationship between organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and job satisfaction so that research findings are interesting for further investigation.

Job satisfaction significantly influences the quality of public services. The finding of this study is consistent with the opinion of [4] saying that the employee/individual performance is significantly associated with the improvement of service quality. Similarly, the results of research by [10] in which one of the results shows that employee satisfaction has a significant direct effect on quality of services delivered at Malang Municipal Revenue Service.

B. Practical Implications

Based on the results of this research, we can argue that a good public service delivered by Magetan District government is significantly affected by employee satisfaction. Employee satisfaction is indirectly influenced by motivation, work environment, and leadership through the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

Therefore, the public service delivery by civil servants (employees) in Magetan district should be based on the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of the employees, thus increasing employee job satisfaction and will produce sizeable impact on providing a good service to the public by those employees. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) constitutes a behavior that is owned by employees who work sincerely beyond their predetermined roles (extra role) in

which they work sincerely, help fellow workers carry out their tasks voluntarily without coercion or requests from colleagues or from the leader. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) can be nurtured by instilling and fostering altruism, conscientiousness, positive attitude, courtesy, and civic virtue of the members.

VIII. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

1. This research doesn't group or categorize respondents' responses of job motivation, work environment, leadership, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), job satisfaction, and public service quality based on the agency/government institution which is used as the unit of analysis (Secretariat, Office, Agency, and Sub-district), thus it is not known exactly whether there is difference in the responses/perception of civil servants on variables to be investigated in this study.
2. This research doesn't group/categorize respondents' responses of the job motivation, work environment, leadership, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), job satisfaction, and quality of public services based on their Rank/Grades, so it is not known definitely whether there is difference in the response/perception of civil servants in Magetan district on the variables used in this study.

In this research, due to limitation in times, the quality of public service is measured based on perception of civil servants working in Magetan district government in which the results may be different when quality of public service is measured based on perception of public who make the use of the service.

IX. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion conducted previously, then we can draw conclusions as follows:

1. Job motivation variable consisting of expectation, instrumentality and valence is positively and significantly associated with organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in Magetan district government. Job motivation has no significant effect on employee satisfaction among civil servants in Magetan district government.
2. Work environment variable including infrastructure, facilities, and coworkers is positively and significantly correlated with organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) Magetan district government. Work environment variable produces no significant impact on employee satisfaction in Magetan district government.
3. Leadership variable encompassing charisma, inspiration, intellectual stimulation, and individualized attention is positively and significantly related to organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in Magetan district government. Leadership variable doesn't bring about significant effect on job satisfaction among employees of Magetan district government.
4. OCB variable made up of altruism, conscientiousness, positive attitude, courtesy, and civic virtue of the members

is positively and significantly associated with employee satisfaction in Magetan district government.

5. Job satisfaction composed of the work itself, job promotion, relationship among employees (coworkers), and working condition produces a positive and significant influence on the quality of public service in Magetan district government.
6. Job motivation indirectly has positive and significant impact on job satisfaction of employees through organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in Magetan district government. This suggests that the OCB as intervening variable mediates the influence of job motivation on employee job satisfaction, because the direct effect of job motivation on job satisfaction is not significant.
7. Work environment indirectly produces positive and significant impact on job satisfaction through organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in Magetan district government. This suggests that the OCB as intervening variable mediates the influence of work environment on job satisfaction, because the direct effect of work environment on employee satisfaction is not significant.
8. Leadership indirectly has positive and significant impact on employee satisfaction through organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in Magetan district government. This suggests that the OCB as intervening variable mediates the influence of leadership on job satisfaction, because the direct effect of leadership on job satisfaction is not significant.

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